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The Story of the Bow and Arrow: Through the Eyes of Children

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine children's metaphorical perceptions and drawings of the traditional concept of Turkish archery. In this study, which aims to uncover and examine metaphorical meanings, the phenomenology pattern was used. The research group was determined through easy-to-access sampling. A total of 60 athletes between the ages of 7 and 12 (40 males and 20 females) who studied in sports schools in the traditional Turkish archery discipline participated in the study in Ankara during the 2020-2021 season. In order to determine the perceptions of the children participating in the research on the concept of traditional Turkish archery through metaphors; "Traditional Turkish archery like/similar; because" and drawing a figure reflecting their thoughts on the concept of traditional Turkish archery. Children who were asked to explain the metaphor they used with the phrase "because" were given sufficient time to complete their figures. Content analysis technique was used in the evaluation of the data. In conclusion; While drawings containing materials specific to the disciplines were encountered in the drawings of the participants, happy human figures who had fun while doing sports were also frequently encountered. The sizes of the materials of the traditional Turkish archery of the children and the drawings were supported by figures containing positive energy such as the sun.

Keywords: Drawing, Metaphor, Phenomenology, Qualitative Research, Sports, Traditional Turkish Archery

1. Introduction

Archery is the oldest sporting art of the early days, but it is still an active sport today (Öngel, 2001). Archery was used to sustain the life of mankind, hunt and sustain its generations, while at the same time being an effective weapon in countering enemies. Equipment such as bows, arrows, horses and tents of the nomadic Turkish people living on Asian steppes has been of great importance in their daily lives. Turks managed to keep this sport alive until the beginning of the 20th century (Bir et al., 2006). Traditional Turkish Archery continues to develop today by being listed by UNESCO as an intangible cultural heritage site in 2019.

Metaphors have many features, from raising the motivation of athletes in traditional Turkish Archery and other sports disciplines, solving cognitive complexes and facilitating learning in teaching new skills in physical

education classes. Metaphors are also used to make sense of many sports-related concepts (İnan et al., 2019). Kövecses (2002) stated in his study that we could establish a relationship between our minds and concepts without changing the actual meaning of the concepts, thanks to metaphors. According to Lakoff and Johnson (2008), most people produce metaphors in our minds and project them on paper as poetry or paintings. In this way, the metaphors expressed by painting get rid of monotony and follow a different path. The fact that there are many analogies in the field of sports is quite prone to creating metaphors on concepts. These concepts also appear in our daily lives (İnan et al., 2019). Gassner (1999) states that using metaphors in teaching sportive skills plays an active role in teaching. In the traditional Turkish archery discipline, which is rapidly becoming widespread today, it is thought that metaphors and drawings are enlightening and guiding in terms of keeping a mirror to the mental processes as well as the physical development of the athletes who learn and want to develop this sport, and to determine the interest needs of the children who adopt the sport.

When the literature is examined, there are different sports disciplines, sports, physical education and sports lessons, and different metaphor studies for the concept of physical education teachers. Hohepa et al. (2006) aimed to explore the opinions of high school students about various physical activity contexts and their ideas about strategies for promoting potential physical activity in their studies. Triggs et al. (2011) focused on the place of the lyrics of children playing ball in the premier league in sports psychology and the communication of the players with each other in their study. Şirin et al. (2012) conducted a research to determine the metaphorical perceptions of rafting participants towards the concept of rafting. Koç et al. (2015) aimed to reveal the perceptions of primary 7th grade students towards the concept of "sports" through metaphors. Karakaya and Salici (2016) presented the study aimed at determining the metaphorical perceptions of 11–13-year-old studying in Isparta about popular sports. Hazar et al. (2017) tried to explain the perceptions of "traditional and digital" games through metaphors in the articles titled "Traditional game and digital game perceptions of middle school students". In their work, Çareदार et al. (2022) examined the perceptions and drawings of children between the ages of 7- 12 towards the concept of basketball. Studies that examine the perceptions and drawings of athletes for their own discipline concepts are rare in sports disciplines.

The subject of how the traditional Turkish archery discipline is expressed by children through metaphors, which is the source of the formation of our thoughts and the emergence of our behaviors, is a subject that needs to be investigated. It is thought that the concept of traditional Turkish archery handed down from generation to generation, the way children understand it is noticed by federations, coaches and families, and the study can contribute to the development of the discipline. Therefore, the aim of this study is to determine the metaphorical perceptions and drawings of children towards the concept of traditional Turkish archery.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

In this study, which aims to uncover and examine the metaphorical meanings that children place on traditional Turkish archery concepts, the phenomenology pattern was used. In a phenomenological study, it is tried to reveal what individuals are experiencing and how they make sense of what they are experiencing (Creswell & Poth, 2016). In interpretative phenomenology, which aims to reveal the hidden meanings in human relations and experiences (Lopez & Willis, 2004).

2.2. Participants

A total of 60 children between the ages of 7-12 (40 males and 20 females) studying at traditional Turkish archery sports schools in Ankara in the 2020-2021 season participated in the research. However, data analyzes were carried out on 54 participants as a result of eliminating the forms that did not want to participate in the study, were not suitable or were empty.

2.3. Data Collection Technique

The data collection tool consists of two parts. In the first part, the demographic characteristics obtained in the research are included, and in the second part, in order to determine the perceptions of the children participating in the research towards the concept of traditional Turkish archery through metaphors; “it is like this, because.....” was obtained through completing the sentence and drawing a figure reflecting their thoughts on the concept of traditional Turkish archery. Children who were asked to explain the metaphor they used with the phrase "because" were given sufficient time to complete their figures. While explaining what to do to the children participating in the research, care was taken not to use any guiding expressions, and necessary permissions were obtained from their families and trainers for the application.

2.3.1. Data Evaluation

In the research, a total of 54 metaphors that were valid for the concept of "traditional archery" were analyzed using content analysis technique. Content analysis; It is the process of quantifying (digitizing) what people say and write by coding them according to clear instructions (Patton, 2014). The metaphors obtained first for the analysis of the data are numbered from 1 to 54. The metaphors and drawings on the numbered papers were examined one by one and coding was made taking into account the explanations. During coding, the data were tried to be made meaningful by creating a code list according to the meanings of the metaphors and reaching the categories that could best explain the relationship between the codes. Metaphors are often used in qualitative research due to their ability to deal with the diversity of research data (ease of creating categories), link data and facilitate the presentation of data to the reader (Sadık & Sarı, 2012). In order to ensure validity and reliability in qualitative research, it was used to submit the data and analyses to the control of the people being investigated, as well as to present the data and the interpretations of the analyses to the experts (Ekiz, 2009). In addition, the themes created by two experts from outside the research and the researcher who conducted the study were compared and the numbers of consensus and disagreement were determined in the comparisons, and the reliability of the research was calculated using Miles and Huberman (1994)'s formula ($\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{consensus}}{\text{consensus} + \text{disagreement}}$). In qualitative studies, a desired level of reliability is achieved when the agreement between expert and researcher evaluations is 90% or more (Saban, 2009; Saban et al., 2006). It was observed that the harmonization percentages of the drawings were collected under the same themes in 92% of the same themes. Again, the delivery of some of the findings without impairing the authenticity of the research results is one of the measures that will increase the internal reliability of the research (Maykut & Morehouse, 2002; Robson, 1999; Türnüklü, 2001; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005). In this study, the process of determining metaphors was described in detail, and one-to-one examples from the statements of the participants were presented in the findings section of the research.

3. Results

In this section, the drawings of licensed and amateur children interested in traditional Turkish archery are examined under certain codes and themes according to their common characteristics and numerical information about them is presented. Examples of drawings are also included. The codes and themes of the metaphors made by the children who participated in the study towards the concept of “traditional turkish archery” are included in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of the metaphors produced by children regarding the concept of traditional Turkish archery and distribution by categories attributed to the subject to the source

Conceptual Themes	Codes
Being a winner	Pen, duster, stick, horse, spear, race and religion, eagle, war, tree, letter 1, security, war tool, circle, flower, airplane, food, volleyball, bow, Turkishness, olympic archery, clean air, pistol, falcon, ball, football, basketball, dodgeball
Being emotional	A place he never knows, game, yoga, sports, history, loving, exhilarating, perseverance
Being a fun	Motivation element, entertainment, time travel, high speed train

3.1 Traditional Turkish Archery as a Gain Element

In addition to the physical development of moving and high pulse training, it is also underlined the contribution it makes to psychosocial and personal development (Malm et al., 2019). They emphasized that the development of skills such as social development self-esteem and self-worth together with personal development supports sports activities (Holt et al., 2017). Research shows that children who participate in sports are also adopted by parents to provide personal social and physical benefits (Neely & Holt, 2014).

In this category, the athletes learn the concept of traditional Turkish archery, useful, good, directing to the right habits, self-control, responsibility, patience, preventing evil, etc. The situations in which they explained the characteristics of the metaphor attributed to the source with expressions were gathered under this category. The metaphors used by 37 athletes (68.5%) in this category are pencil, dust breaker, stick, horse, spear, race and religion, eagle, war, tree, letter I, security, war tool, hoop, flower, airplane, food, volleyball, bow, Turkish, Olympic archery, fresh air, pistol, falcon, ball, football, basketball, dodgeball metaphors can be given as examples. Some examples of metaphors and drawings created by athletes interested in traditional Turkish archery are given below;

“Traditional Turkish Archery is/like our roots; because it is a strong sport that has developed since the beginning of our history and will continue forever, and it is an important factor in transferring our history to the future.” (Athlete 27E13)

“Traditional Turkish Archery is/like a hawk; Because in Turkish archery, you focus on your target and shoot, just like a falcon focuses on its target and glides through the sky to catch its prey.” (Athlete 12E11)

Figure 1:(a-b): Traditional Turkish Archery as a Gain Element

For figure 1a, archery can be preferred as a sport with a high sense of curiosity and fun. His detailed drawing in the figure shows that he has a perfectionist structure and gives importance to archery. (Athlete 51E9)

For figure 1b, we can think of archery as a sport that one can have fun and enjoy. The fact that he is not afraid of obstacles while focusing on the goal can mean that the motivation is high. (Athlete 29K10)

3.2 Traditional Turkish Archery as a Fun-Motivation Element

In sports disciplines, there are many elements that connect the athletes to themselves and provide motivation and fun. Motivation enables a person to increase their desire and effort to realize learning. Maintaining this desire and effort makes teaching and learning processes fun and efficient (Ur, 1996). Naturally, children love games and they are interested in lessons and training with fun activities. In other words, success comes as a result of being well motivated (Yule, 2006).

When this theme is examined, it is seen that the drawings are concentrated as figures of happy children in traditional Turkish archery training. It is seen in the drawings and metaphors that children consider the time when

they are happy and enjoying while learning the concept of traditional Turkish archery. Some examples of metaphors and drawings created by children are as follows:

“Traditional Turkish Archery is like/like love; Because shooting is a fun and relaxing sport, I feel good while shooting arrows.” (Athlete 22K9)

“Traditional Turkish Archery is/is like a fun game; because it's fun to play games, it's fun to shoot arrows” (Athlete7E10)

Figure 2: (a-b-c). Traditional Turkish Archery as a Fun-Motivation Element

From the drawings of figure 2a, it can be said that archery makes her happy and good, and it can be said that it will be a factor in increasing the motivation of the athlete and increasing her success. (Athlete 22K9)

In the statement he made in figure 2b as "My dream is to be 1st in the competition and to score 10", we can say that he has a clear personality and goal-oriented with his drawings, and that his goal is a small bow and his drawing himself big reflects his self-confidence. (Athlete 30E8)

In figure 2c, we can understand that the athlete enjoys sports by keeping all parts of her body facing the target, and some of the drawings have faint or missing limb drawings. Self-confidence and social personality areas can be given importance. (Athlete 28K13)

3.3 Traditional Turkish Archery as an Emotion Element

Emotions play a central role in the important events of our lives. Although emotions have many behavioral and physiological characteristics, emotions are primarily psychological (Lazarus, 1991). They are subjective feelings experienced in response to events in the athlete's mind, such as the athlete's environment or the anticipation of an upcoming event (Lazarus, 2000). Emotional intelligence inspires not only to achieve better but also to enthusiastically start an activity, even if it is an extremely challenging task (Goleman, 2017). Effective learning takes place as long as children have fun and actively participate in the learning process (Uskan & Bozkuş, 2019). In this category, a place where the athletes do not know the concept of traditional Turkish archery, games, yoga, sports, history, love, pleasure, perseverance, etc. explained in terms. Examples of metaphors used by 12 students (22.2%) in this category are hobby, being stress-free, relaxing, liking sports, distraction, having fun while shooting arrows, and curiosity. Some examples of metaphors and drawings created by athletes are as follows:

“Traditional Turkish Archery is like/similar to entering a place I have never known; Because when I shoot an arrow, I try to aim the arrow like everyone else, but I still wonder if the arrow will go to the target and I get excited.” (Athlete51E9)

“Traditional Turkish Archery is like/similar to entering yoga; because even though my lessons are tiring for me, I distract myself in archery and it relaxes me.” (Athlete 35E9)

Figure 3(a-b): Traditional Turkish Archery as an Emotion Element

We can say that he puts regular work on the basis of his success and his motivation is strong with the explanation of figure 3a, "If we do not stop working, we will shoot like this arrow". (Athlete 21K8)

In figure 3b, we can state that she draws her figure in three dimensions, sees the details well, and emphasizes her self-confidence by keeping the bow clear. We can say that she likes traditional Turkish archery with her happy facial expression, which she is sure that she will succeed in drawing that the arrows she shoots hit the target. (Athlete 16K9)

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Metaphors and drawings were used in this study to determine the feelings and thoughts of children studying traditional Turkish archery towards the concept of traditional Turkish archery. While drawings of the participants contained materials specific to the discipline, happy human figures who had fun while playing sports were also frequently found. The size of the materials drawn by the children in traditional Turkish archery supported the drawings with figures with positive energy such as the sun. Due to the Covid 19 pandemic, they have to spend most of the day in front of electronic devices in a sedentary house, which they define as a relaxing and focused activity that distracts traditional Turkish archery from the cognitive fatigue created by lessons and daily life.

The positive development of the sports environment involves learning health habits and being physically fit. Positive development also includes the development of psychological traits and tendencies (optimism or a sense of hope) and certain skills (the ability to set goals or manage stress) (Gould & Carson, 2008). Given the findings, it is not surprising that professionals in the field of physical education, sport psychology and youth development are interested in using sport as a tool for developing life skills in youth. In addition, in various studies, he emphasized that the family is critical for increasing the commitment of the family to sports and the participation of athletes in training (Ferguson et al., 2019). Social interaction is considered a basic psychological need, which is important for all people (Baumeister & Leary, 2017; Ryan & Deci, 2000). Extroversion throughout life follows a common trajectory that increases in childhood, decreases throughout adolescence, stabilizes in adulthood and decreases in old age (Bleidorn & Hopwood, 2019; Roberts et al., 2006; Van den Akker et al., 2014). Extroversion can be defined more broadly, including talkativeness, sociability, dominance, enterprise, the search for excitement, self-confidence and positive emotions (Wilt & Revelle, 2017). It was observed that some of the paintings had faint or missing limb drawings. It can be suggested that emphasis should be placed on the self-confidence and social personality areas of these athletes and that their sports activities should be supported by their families and coaches. Coaches should help and encourage athletes to realize the importance of emotions in motor performance (Goleman, 2017).

With the findings of the research, it is recommended to carry out various studies with licensed athletes in sports with different age groups in order to benefit from the positive effects it provides by conducting wider research on Turkish archery, which has been transferred from our history to the present, and to benefit from the assimilation of our history by our children. As a result of the findings obtained from the research, the following suggestions can be made:

- In order to enable children to reveal their potential and to determine what they expect from the discipline, it is thought that the study will contribute to the trainers and federations, and by supporting such studies, importance can be given to determining the needs of the children in order to develop the discipline.
- It can be suggested that the developmental characteristics of children should be better absorbed by the coaches and that seminars and trainings should be given on what kind of practices will support the development of athletes.
- In the research findings, more extensive studies can be carried out on this subject in order for our children to assimilate the connection of traditional Turkish archery with our history and to transfer our glorious history from generation to generation.

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